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Role of Ginkgo leaf extract on Cyclopentolate produced memory defects in Zebra fish for the model of Alzheimer's disease

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Abstract

In this research zebra fish induced by scopolamine was investigated by the effect of Ginkgo leaf extract on preventing memory impairment. I divided into 6 groups of male zebra fish including the control of Cyclopentolate 0.003ml/l to 0.006ml/l(Cyc), Cyclopentolate plus Physostigmine 0.5mg/kg (Physostigmine+Cyc), and Cyclopentolate plus extract at doses of 4,8,10mg/kg (Ginkgo 4+Cyc, Ginkgo 8mg/kg+Cyc, and Ginkgo 10mg/kg), In T-maze test the spatial memory evaluated by the conditional and the measurement of fear memory done by the inhibitory avoidance test by T-maze. The results showed that the Physostigmine+Cyc group had the best time spent ratio in the T-maze by the spatial memory test, followed by Ginkgo 4mg/kg+Cyc, Ginkgo 8mg/kg+Cyc, Ginkgo 10mg/kg+Cyc, control and Cyc group, respectively, but no statistical significance. For Ginkgo leaf at dose of 4, 8 and 10mg/kg had significantly increased latency time as 21.78 ± 4.62 , 23.78 ± 13.04 and 18.23 ± 18.87 min respectively. For the fear memory test of Zebra fish, when compared to the Cyc group (9.83 ± 10.48 min). These result suggested that inhibitory avoidance test related to fear memory by the Ginkgo leaf extract attenuated memory impairment. I found that it is very useful for further research for the development of Ginkgo leaf extract as a health product to develop the symptoms of Alzheimer's disease.

Keywords: Ginkgo leaf extract, Zebra fish, Alzheimer's disease

Introduction

The Alzheimer diseases was described by scientist alois Alzheimer in 1901. He explained the clinical and pathological findings a 51 years old woman with a progressive dementia of 4.5 year course it meconized as a disonder bearing her name this is beings with a remembering difficulty of a new information due to the distribution of brain cells in regions, forming new memories the people experience irritability, depression and anxiety in early mild and moderate stage. In other stage also happens outbursts emotional distness, mestlessness, sleep disturbances etc. the various symptoms and stage of Alzheimer's is described

1st stage: mild cognitive impairment it's duration 7 years. Disease beings in medical temporal lobe. It's symptoms short term memory loss

2nd stage: Mild alzheimer's - it's duration 2 years. in this stage disease spreads to lateral, temporal and parietal lobes it's symptoms are reading problems, poor direction sense.

3rd stage: Moderate alzheimer's It's duration 2 years. it spreads to frontal lobes. It's symptoms are poor judgment and short attention

4th stage: Severe Alzheimer's it's duration 3 years. it spreads to occipital lobes. It's symptoms includes visuals problems. The ginkgo leaf extract is a natural products which is used in the treatment of asthma, bronchitis, fatigue and to prevent dementia and improve memory. My present study examined the pharmacological properties of ginkgo leaf extract to prevent Cyclopentolate include learning defects in zebra fish that explain basic neuro system organization as models of humans neurological didease. The present effects of ginkgo leaf extract on Cyclopentolate induced memory defects in zebra fish investigated to entrance of ginkgo leaf ectract as possible dietary supplement or medicine for the aneliomantion of the onset of alzheimer's disease.

Material and Methods

1. The ginkgo leaf extract preparation

The leaves of ginkgo biloba (Ginkgoaceae) collected from the lab which is came from Siberia after collected from Malbazar by lab and then it is washed, dried and powdered in a coarse

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manners by using a blender. The process maceration was employed for extraction using deionized water as a solvent at 60°C for 6 hours (100 gm of plant leaf per 1 litre of water) then after the filtrate was collected and the solvent was removed by freezing (lyophilization) then the dry extract powder was stored in a light proof container at -20 °C and dissolved in distilled water before use.

2. Polyphenolic compound determination of ginkgo leaf extract

The polyphenolic compounds in ginkgo leaf extracts used for the measurement by using reversed phase HPLC in brief details a diode array detector and a reversed phase column (DAD – HPLC) method was followed for the determination of polyphenolic compounds in ginkgo leaf extract using ten standards, including gallic acid, eriodictyol, kaempferol, luteolin of phenolic compounds which were chromatographed by HPLC using UV-vis diode array detection. The detector was set at 277nm mainly for phenolic acids and was set at 357nm for flavonoids.

3. T-maze test conditioning for colour biased appetite

In this training session zebra fish were placed in the terminal of long arm, the sliding door opened to allow the fish can swim towards the short arm after 1 minute. Another sliding door at the junction was closed when once the fish entered any of the short arms, as observed for 5 minute the fish were authorized to swim to the green arm, it was fed by food. It was returned to repeat training for 3 days if the fish swam to the red arm during the testing session fish entered the by performing the same test in the training process with no punishment in the red arm and without food in green arm. When time spent and total number entries into the red arm and green arm were evaluated.

4. Animals

We take thirty adult male zebra fish (*Danio rerio*) with body length 3-5 cm and 500mg weight were cultured in an acrylic tank with reverse osmosis water and oxygen keeping the water in the tank for 24 hours before use the density was per 7.5 litres of 5 fish. Water PH and temperature were maintained at 6.5 – 7.5 and 28±2°C respectively with 12 hours light to dark cycle. With artemia twice a day 9 morning – evening) the fish were fed. Fish were kept in holding tanks for 7 days before the experiment. Before feeding the zebra fish were weighed. By a damp cloth the fish were placed and by using a plastic catheter connected micropipette then they were fed.

The zebra fishes are divided into 6 groups

Group 1: Control (fed by water)

Group 2: Cyc (produced by Cyclopentolate)

Group 3: Physostigmine+Cyc (Produced by Cyclopentolate and fed with Physostigmine 0.5mg/kg)

Group 4: Ginkgo 4+Cyc (induced by Cyclopentolate and fed with Ginkgo 4mg/kg)

Group 5: Ginkgo 8+Cyc (induced by Cyclopentolate and fed with Ginkgo 8mg/kg)

Group 6: Ginkgo 10+Cyc (induced by Cyclopentolate and fed with Ginkgo 10mg/kg)

For 14 days before the behavioral test each group received the dosages. All experiments were carried out by the lab.

- 5. Behavioral Test Apparatus:** I know the colour biased appetite conditioning T-maze test and inhibitory avoidance test consisted by the experimental apparatus. T-maze test was prepared as acrylic glass T-Shaped maze, dimensions 50cm×10cm×10cm for the long arm and dimensions 20cm×10cm×10cm for two short arms by the tank for the colour biased appetite. The inhibitory avoidance test for a tank, an acrylic glass with aquarium dimensions of 18cm×9cm×7cm, was divided into two equal dark and white compartments by a sliding door. The electrical stimulator with an electrode plate connected was placed in the dark compartment.
- 6. Experimental Procedure:** In this procedure the physostigmine and the Ginkgo leaf extract fed to zebra fish for 2 hours before start the experiment and before the experiment for 1 hour the fish were treated with 0.003ml/l to 0.006ml/l Cyclopentolate solution. The standard and the extract solution were fresh by prepared on the dry of the experiment. The experiment was done for 42 days. However there were no statistically significant differences between the results.
- 7. Inhibitory Avoidance Test:** Zebra fish were placed in the white compartment in the training day. After 1 minute the fish authorized to enter the dark compartment while the sliding door opened 1cm above the tank floor. When the zebra fish entered the dark compartment the sliding door was suddenly closed. Then for 2 seconds a 3mA shock current was applied. In next day in the testing session same procedure following as the training session without an electrical shock. The latency time to enter the dark compartment was investigated in both the testing and training session.
- 8. Statistical Analysis:** The performance of statistical analysis sigma plot (version 12.0) all values was analyzed using one-way ANOVA and as mean ± SEM and tukey's post hoc tests. Differences between groups were considered statistically significant at P value <0.05

Results

- 1. Polyphenolic compound determination of Ginkgo Leaf Extract:** I found many polyphenolic compounds in ginkgo leaf extract including flavonoids quercetin, kaempferol, luteolin, apigenin isorhamnetin in ginkgo leaf extract.
- 2. The T-maze test for conditioning the colour biased:** The time spent and mean arm test were calculated to find the mean difference (green arm /red arm) and total number of entries in the green arm. With a mean difference for group of time spent and total number of entries more than 1, it was interpreted that zebra fish spent more time in the green arms than red arms suggesting that zebra fish in these groups showed a very good memory performance zebra fish received Physostigmine and ginkgo leaf extract at all dosage showed mean difference of time spent and total number of entries at more than however result were not statistically significant. Zebra fish that received ginkgo leaf extract of 4mg/kg, 8mg/kg and 10mg/kg recorded greater total number of entries ratio than the control and longer time spent ratio and Cyclopentolate groups. However there were no statistically significant difference between the results the green arm. With a mean difference for groups of time spent and total number of

entries more than 1, it was interpreted that zebra fish spent more time in the green arms than red arms, suggesting that zebra fish in these groups showed a very good memory performance zebra fish received Physostigmine and ginkgo leaf extract at all dosage showed mean difference of entries at more than however results were not statistically significant. Zebra fish are received ginkgo leaf extract of 4mg/kg, 8mg/kg, 10mg/kg recorded greater the total number of entries ratio than the control and longer time spent ratio and Cyc groups. However there were no statistically significant differences between the results.

- 3. Inhibitory avoidance test:** In this test zebra fish received the ginkgo leaf extract doses of 4, 8 and 10mg/kg significantly increased time latency as 21.78 ± 4.62 , 23.78 ± 13.04 and 18.23 ± 18.87 min respectively, compared to the Cyclopentolate group (-9.83 ± 10.48 min). In this addition I found there were no statistically significant different among doses of ginkgo leaf extracts. These results explained that ginkgo leaf extracts at all doses was effective against memory impairment produced by Cyclopentolate, especially fear memory in zebra fish.

Discussion

As this research I know the effect of Ginkgo leaf extract important for preventing the dementia produced in zebra fish by Cyclopentolate was investigated. I know Cyclopentolate is a muscarinic receptor this increases AChE activity in the cortex and levels for the oxidative stress and proinflammatory cytokines in the hippocampus as well it will be increased levels of Tau and APP by producing amyloid to produce neurodegeneration that can cause Alzheimer's disease. As we can use Cyclopentolate as a toxin to produce zebrafish memory impairment for the study. If we used Physostigmine as a positive control for replicate the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. As the behavioural testing evaluate the effect on learning and memory of Zebrafish. As the methods include the colour based appetite conditioning inhibitory avoidance test and T-maze test. I use T-maze for test used time spent in green arm and red arm as an indicator for testing and learning and memory of zebra fish. After the research I widely accept that Ginkgo leaf extract possess a good memory recovering activities of zebra fish. The ginkgo leaf extracts contains phytochemicals like kaempferol, Quercetin, Leuteolin, Apigenin and isorhamnetin that produced the neuroprotective effects of flavonoids might be due to a reduction in oxidative stress. Our research explained ginkgo leaf extracts show potential for prevention and treatment of Alzheimer's disease or memory impairment and for memory defect 0.003ml/l working properly so, I not increase the dosage.

Conclusion

Effect of ginkgo leaf extract on Cyclopentolate produced memory defects in zebra fish were investigated. My research is useful for further research and development of ginkgo leaf extract as a healthy product to ameliorate memory impairment or Alzheimer's disease in future. But according my knowledge for a good research individual publication or groupwise research publication is very important. For the Impact factor research work very important as I know. The research impact factor for academics/R&D/Company are- $E_{q1} = \frac{\text{Total number of research citations}}{\text{Total numbers of research partners including}}$

$\text{me} + \frac{\text{Total no of research citations (individually)}}{\text{me}}$
 Research Impact Factor = $\frac{E_{q1}}{\text{Total amount of citable publications (in this year) + Total amount of citable publications in previous year + Total amount of individual publication/4 + Degree/4 years/Degree + Bed/4 years}}$ (1-mark if nor 0) + Masters(1) + Phd(1) + Experience as a Faculty in college or Officer/Executive in any Company or Researcher/Scientist in any company.
 If 50 above - Outstanding, 40-49.9 - Excellent, 30-39.9 - Very Good, 20-29.9 - High Satisfactory, 10-19.9 - Satisfactory, 5-9.9 - Less Satisfactory, 2-4.9 - Poor, 0.1-1.9 - Very Poor

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